

A Near-Infrared view on Multiple Populations in Globular Clusters among VLM stars

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Abstract

High-precision near-infrared (NIR) photometry, as shown by past-years works, is able to disentangle different stellar populations in Globular Clusters (GCs) among very-low-mass (VLM) stars, a regime that has been poorly explored in this scientific context. In this work, I summarize the main results from the study of Dondoglio et al. (2022), where we analyzed nine Galactic GCs and the open cluster NGC 6791 with archive Hubble Space Telescope (HST) observations in the NIR filters F110W and F160W, which are able to spot multiple populations thanks to the oxygen sensitivity of the F110W-F160W color. We found that multiple populations are a widespread phenomenon also in the VLM regime, detecting the variety and the dependence on GC mass that also characterize the phenomenon at higher stellar masses. Combining the NIR photometry here presented with ultraviolet (UV) and optical observation allows measuring, for the first time, the Mass Function (MF) of multiple populations along the whole Main Sequence (MS) of NGC 2808 and NGC,6121, covering a stellar mass range of $\sim 0.2\text{-}0.8 M_{\odot}$. We found that multiple populations share the same MF slope in both GCs, suggesting that the properties of the phenomenon do not depend on stellar mass. This result suggests that the chemically-different stars also share the same initial MF and, by assuming that the second-generation stars formed in a more centrally-concentrated environment than the first-generation stars, also corroborates the idea that the initial MF does not depend on the density of the formation environment.

1 Introduction

Despite the presence of stellar populations with different light-element abundances (i.e., He, C, N, O, Na among others) in Globular Clusters (GCs) is now widely accepted, we are still lacking a comprehensive explanation to justify this phenomenon (also referred to as the multiple populations phenomenon). Stars in GCs are usually classified into two categories: the ones with a chemical composition that resembles Milky Way halo stars, dubbed first generation (1G) stars, and the others with unique patterns of light-elements abundances, that we observe only inside GCs, which are usually referred to as second generation (2G) stars (see Bastian & Lardo 2018, Gratton *et al.* 2019, Milone & Marino 2022 for recent reviews).

From the last ~ 15 years of studies, two main groups of formation scenarios emerged so far as the most appealing ones. The first category foresees multiple star formation episodes: as intermediate-to-high mass stars formed during the first starburst evolve, they eject winds of processed material that pollute the pristine star-forming intra-cluster medium, from which 2G stars subsequently form. Among the proposed polluters, we can find intermediate-mass asymptotic giant branch (AGB) stars, fast-rotating massive stars, supermassive stars, or massive interacting binaries (e.g., Ventura *et al.* 2001, Decressin *et al.* 2007, de Mink *et al.* 2009, D’Ercole *et al.* 2010, Krause *et al.* 2013, D’Antona *et al.* 2016, Calura *et al.* 2019). The second class of scenarios is instead based on only one star formation episode, where the ejecta of very massive stars are accreted by forming low-mass protostars (e.g., Denissenkov & Hartwick 2014, Gieles *et al.* 2018).

To test different scenarios and put constraints on the mechanisms that formed multiple populations, retrieving new in-

formation is crucial. To do that, the Very-Low Mass (VLM) stars regime is a potential goldmine to increase our knowledge of this mysterious phenomenon. They are M-dwarf stars that belong to the bottom of the Main Sequence (MS), with masses smaller than $\sim 0.4 M_{\odot}$. As a consequence these stars are very faint, making their observation particularly challenging, especially in the multiple-populations context, where high-precision photometry is mandatory. Exploring 1G and 2G among VLM stars was made possible by the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) and its Near Infrared Channel of the Wide Field Camera 3 (WFC3/NIR), thanks to which chemically different populations were disentangled at such faint magnitudes (e.g., Milone *et al.* 2012a, 2014, 2017a; Milone *et al.* 2019, Dotter *et al.* 2015, Bellini *et al.* 2018) by exploiting the F110W-F160W color. Indeed, a strong contribution to VLM stars’ absorption comes from oxygen-based molecules (Allard & Hauschildt, 1995), to which the F160W band is sensitive so that the oxygen-different 1G and 2G stars can be effectively separated.

Being able to disentangle multiple populations along the whole MS gives the unique opportunity to study their Mass Functions (MFs). The only observational work on this topic comes from Milone *et al.* (2012b), which studied the MF of three He-different populations in NGC 2808 among a mass range of $\sim 0.75\text{-}0.45 M_{\odot}$. By considering also the VLM stars, we can reach lower masses, allowing us to draw firmer conclusions on their fundamental characteristics, such as their slopes.

The MF slopes play a pivotal role in constraining different formation scenarios. Indeed, in the accretion on protostar formation scenarios, we expect that the amount of accreted gas, and therefore the properties of 2G stars, would depend

Figure 1: *Upper panels:* from left to right, NIR CMDs of the GCs NGC 2808, NGC 5904, M 4, and of the OC NGC 6791. The grey boxes highlight (qualitatively) the VLM stars. Color error bars are shown in red. *Middle and lower panels:* $\Delta_{F110W,F160W}$ kernel-density distribution of M dwarf between F160W 0.5 and 2.5 magnitudes below the MS knee expected from observational errors only (orange) and observed (black). See Dondoglio et al. (2022) for the full-sample image.

on the mass of the accreting object. This leads to differences between the MF slopes of chemically different populations. As predicted by Ballesteros-Paredes *et al.* (2015) in the case of a Bondi-Hoyle-Littleton accretion for a Kroupa (Kroupa, 2001) IMF, a stellar population formed by the proposed mechanism is expected to have a MF slope of -2 which, at least in the low mass regime that we are exploring, is significantly different from a Kroupa IMF of slope ~ -1.3 .

In this paper, I describe the main results obtained in Dondoglio *et al.* (2022), where we analyzed archive HST observations in the F110W and F160W NIR filters taken with the HST of nine GCs and one Galactic open cluster to investigate their VLM stars, performing the first multiple populations census in this uncharted stellar mass regime. We then used these observations to explore, for the first time, the presence

of differences between different populations' MF slopes or lack thereof over the whole MS mass regime of two GCs of our sample, namely NGC 2808 and NGC 6121. The next Sections are organized as follows: Section 2 shows the Color-Magnitude Diagrams (CMDs) of all the clusters in the analyzed sample, describing the properties that arise from inspecting them. Section 3 is dedicated to our results on the Mass Functions (MFs) measurement of multiple populations in NGC 2808 and M 4. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the main outcomes and implications of this work.

2 Near-Infrared Color-Magnitude Diagram

We show the resulting m_{F160W} vs. $m_{F110W} - m_{F160W}$ CMDs of four clusters of our sample, namely NGC 2808, NGC 5904, NGC 6121, and NGC 6791, in Figure 1. In the first

Figure 2: VLM stars width, $W_{F110W,F160W}$, plotted against cluster metallicity (left), the logarithm of cluster mass (middle), and average oxygen difference between 2G and 1G stars inferred from spectroscopy (right). The black dots indicate the NGC 6791 measurements. The Spearman's rank correlation coefficients for GC measurements are quoted in each panel.

three, the VLM stars are spread along a color interval not consistent with the photometric errors alone, while in the last one, they form a narrow sequence. These because NGC 6791 is the open cluster in our sample, in which we do not expect the presence of multiple populations. On the other hand, in the three GCs, the presence of star-to-star oxygen variations leads to the wide color distribution along stars below the MS knee (i.e., the saddle at ~ 2 -3 mag below the turn-off). A visual analysis also suggests that the phenomenon does not behave exactly in the same way in different GCs. Indeed, while M 4 two sequences are clearly visible, NGC 5904 presents a continuous spread in color, with obvious separation between its stars. The other GC, NGC 2808, shows two sequences characterized by a less net separation. The lower panels of the Figure quantify this visual impression, showing the verticalized color distribution of VLM stars, $\Delta_{F110W,F160W}$, between 0.5 and 2.5 mag below the MS knee, obtained as in Milone *et al.* (2017b). Here, the distribution expected from observational errors is highlighted in orange, while the observed one is colored in black. The three GCs, as expected, show a significantly larger distribution, while for NGC 6791 the two are similar. The observed distribution of both NGC 2808 and M 4 VLM stars displays two peaks, while no discreteness is observable in NGC 5904.

To quantify the amount of F110W-F160W spread, the color width $W_{F110W,F160W}$ was introduced, defined as the difference between the 4th and the 96th percentile of the color of VLM stars that lie within a ± 0.2 mag wide interval located 2 F160W magnitudes below the MS knee. To this quantity, the color width of observational errors was subtracted to consider only the intrinsic MS width, introduced by the presence of multiple populations. This quantity ranges from ~ 0.06 to 0.15 for GCs, and it is consistent with zero in the open cluster NGC 6791. Figure 2 shows the relations with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ (Harris, 1996), total cluster mass (Baumgardt & Hilker, 2018), and $[\text{O}/\text{Fe}]$ difference between 1G and 2G stars from RGB spectroscopy (Marino *et al.*, 2019), portrayed in the left, middle, and right panel, respectively. This quantity does not correlate with the metallicity, while it strongly correlates with both the cluster mass and the oxygen variation inferred from

spectroscopy.

3 Mass Function of Multiple Populations in NGC 2808 and M 4

To derive the MF of the chemically-different populations in NGC 2808 and M 4, two different magnitude intervals have been considered to cover both the MS region between the turn-off and the knee and below the knee (hereafter upper and lower MS, respectively). While for the lower MS we used the CMDs shown in Figure 1, for the upper MS other photometric combinations, involving UV and optical photometry, were necessary. In the left panel of Figure 3 is illustrated the m_{F160W} vs. $m_{F390W}-m_{F160W}$ CMD of NGC 2808, in which three sequences are visible in the $18.5 < m_{F160W} < 20.5$ range, thanks to their He differences (Piotto *et al.*, 2007). As proven by Milone *et al.* (2012a), the MS with blue $m_{F110W}-m_{F160W}$, hereafter MS-I, is the counterpart of the redder upper MS, while the upper middle and blue MSs merge into the red lower MS (MS-II). MS-I contains 1G and the less extreme 2G stars, whereas the MS-II only contains extreme 2G stars. Regarding M 4, by combining the $C_{F275W,F336W,F438W} = m_{F275W} - 2m_{F336W} + m_{F438W}$ pseudo-color (right panel) and the $m_{F275W}-m_{F438W}$, it is possible to build the Chromosome Map (ChM¹) represented in the inset, in which two blobs of stars centered at $(\Delta_{F275W,F438W}, \Delta_{CF275W,F336W,F438W}) \sim (-0.10, 0.05)$ and $(-0.15, 0.30)$ are well separated. The first is populated by 1G stars (the blue sequence in the NIR CMD), whereas the latter consists of M 4 2G stars, and it is the counterpart of the red sequence in the VLM regime.

After disentangling multiple populations along both MS regimes, the next step is to compute their MFs. First, we measured the fraction of both populations identified in the two GCs at different m_{F160W} bins, obtaining their Luminosity Functions (LFs). LFs are then transformed into MFs through the Dartmouth stellar models (Dotter *et al.*, 2008),

¹The ChM is a photometric diagram that combines two color and/or pseudo-color to maximize the information on multiple populations. See Milone *et al.* (2015, 2017b) for details.

Figure 3: *Left panel*: m_{F160W} vs. $m_{F390W}-m_{F160W}$ CMD of NGC 2808. *Right panel*: m_{F160W} vs. $m_{F390W}-m_{F160W}$ pseudo-CMD of M 4. The inset displays the $\Delta_{CF275W, F336W, F438W}$ vs. $\Delta_{F275W, F438W}$ ChM for the MS stars within the grey rectangle.

providing a mass-magnitude relation useful to convert the observed m_{F160W} into stellar mass. The obtained MFs are shown in Figure 4. Red points represent the fraction of MS-I and 1G stars in NGC 2808 (left panel) and M 4 (right panel), respectively, while cyan points are the measured values for the MS-II and 2G populations. The slopes are derived by fitting the observed distribution with straight lines. Both clusters’ populations share the same observed slopes within uncertainties, as reported in their respective panels.

4 Conclusions

The high-precision photometry in the HST NIR filters F110W and F160W derived in this work proved that the multiple populations phenomenon is a widespread phenomenon in GCs also among VLM stars, providing an early census of the phenomenon in this still relatively unexplored (in the multiple populations context) stellar regime. All of the studied GCs show a $m_{F110W}-m_{F160W}$ color larger than the contribution of the observational error, which is associated with the presence of stars with different oxygen abundances, whereas the open cluster NGC 6791, in which we do not expect multiple populations (e.g., Bragaglia *et al.*, 2014; Boberg *et al.*, 2016), presents a narrow lower MS.

The variety of the observed multiple-population patterns among different clusters highlights the complexity of the phenomenon, since the properties (i.e., discrete/continuous distribution, width) change between different clusters among our sample. Noticeably, the fact that also these fully-convective M dwarf stars host multiple populations corroborates the evidence that the phenomenon has not had an evolutionary origin, but is rather established at their formation.

Combining the photometry here presented with UV and optical observation gives the possibility of separating multiple populations among the whole MS stellar mass range, and therefore measuring the MF of the different populations from the turn-off to the bottom of the MS. The cases of NGC 2808

and NGC 6121, where archive data allow separating different populations along the whole MS, show that there is no significant difference between different populations’ slopes within observational errors. This fact is in conflict with the formation scenarios that foresee accretion on protostars, since the phenomenon would depend on stellar mass, causing the different populations to have different slopes, which is the opposite of what we observed.

Furthermore, the MF measurement also gives insights into the nature of multiple populations’ initial MF (MF). Indeed, according to N-body simulations performed by Vesperini *et al.* (2018), in dynamically old GCs, large differences in present-day local and global MF slopes are expected only when the different populations formed with different IMF. Since 2G stars are believed to be formed in a more centrally concentrated environment than 1G stars, this result suggests that the IMF, at least in the subsolar mass regime, does not depend on the formation environment.

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Figure 4: MFs of the two populations identified along the whole MS in NGC 2808 and M4 (left and right panel, respectively). Cyan and red dots represent He-poor and He-rich for NGC 2808 and 1G and 2G in M4. The dot-dashed grey lines indicate the best-fit straight line, with slopes reported in the plots, whereas the black horizontal bars display the mass bin covered by every single point.

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